

Survey

Please complete the survey below.

Thank you!

Study ID

Race

What is your race? Mark one or more boxes.

- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Black or African American
- Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
- White
- Some other race

Ethnicity

Are you of Hispanic or Latino origin?

- Yes, of Hispanic or Latino origin
- No, not of Hispanic or Latino origin

Age

What is your age?

Age in years. For babies less than 1 year old, write 0 as the age

Sex

What is your biological sex assigned at birth?

- Male
- Female
- Intersex
- None of these describe me

[reset](#)

Education

How many years of education have you completed?

Years of education from 0 - 20+

Domicile

Zip or Postal Code:

5-digit zip code

Employment

Are you employed?

- Employed in a permanent position
- Employed in a temporary position
- Not currently employed

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Insurance Status

What kind of health insurance do you have?

- Private insurance
- Public insurance
- None

[reset](#)

Disability Status

Are you deaf or do you have serious difficulty hearing?

- Yes
- No

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Are you blind or do you have serious difficulty seeing, even when wearing glasses?

- Yes
- No

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Because of a physical, mental, or emotional condition, do you have serious difficulty concentrating, remembering, or making decisions?

- Yes
- No

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Do you have serious difficulty walking or climbing stairs?

- Yes
- No

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Do you have difficulty dressing or bathing?

- Yes
- No

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Because of a physical, mental, or emotional condition, do you have difficulty doing errands alone such as visiting a doctor's office or shopping?

- Yes
- No

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Medical History

Vaping Use

- Yes
- No

[reset](#)

Nicotine Use

- Yes
- No

[reset](#)

Alcohol Use

- Yes
- No

[reset](#)

Asthma

- Yes
- No

[reset](#)

Cancer

- Yes
- No

[reset](#)

Cardiovascular disease	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Chronic kidney disease	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Chronic lung disease	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Diabetes	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Hypertension	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Immunosuppressive condition	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Serious mental illness	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Sickle cell disease	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Symptoms		
Cough	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Fever	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Shortness of breath or difficulty breathing	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Headache	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset
Muscle ache	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	reset

New loss of taste or smell

- Yes
 No

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Chills

- Yes
 No

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Excessive fatigue

- Yes
 No

[reset](#)

Nausea/vomiting

- Yes
 No

[reset](#)

Diarrhea

- Yes
 No

[reset](#)

Abdominal pain

- Yes
 No

[reset](#)

Skin rash

- Yes
 No

[reset](#)

Conjunctivitis

- Yes
 No

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Health status

What is your height?

feet
 in

What is your weight?

Weight in pounds

Would you say that (your) health in general is excellent, very good, good, fair or poor?

- Excellent
 Very good
 Good
 Fair
 Poor

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Submit